

THE ROLE OF NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL ENVIRONMENTAL ETHICS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ATTITUDES TOWARDS THE NATURAL ENVIRONMENT

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Annotation: This article describes national and universal environmental moral standards, environmental qualities of a person in the current situation, attitude to nature, spiritual and moral criteria. The historical experience of mankind is the basis for environmentally sustainable development, expressed not only in science, technology, technological development, but also in their intellectual potential, spiritual and cultural level, and the requirements of the time.

Key words: globalization, ecological education, ecological situation, ecological spiritual and moral criteria, "nature-society", ecological moral norms, environment.

In the current context of globalization, socio-political relations are determined by the ecological qualities of the individual, the spiritual and moral criteria of attitude to nature. In this case, the following indicators are important, namely: first, the compliance of the subjective ecological, spiritual and moral needs of the individual with the objective necessity of practical activities of nature protection; secondly, to reconcile the economic and material needs of the individual in relation to nature with the ecological interests of society; third, the realization that the improvement of the ecological situation is the basis of its existence and the way of life of future generations; fourth, to assess and organize all areas of social and practical activities in accordance with environmental, moral and ethical criteria; fifth, ways to increase environmental activism and responsibility,

Indeed, the “nature-society” relationship can be wisely managed and secured by individuals who are ecologically spiritually and morally perfect. The historical experience of mankind proves that the basis of ecologically sustainable development is not only science, technology, technological development, but also the intellectual potential of the subject, the spiritual and cultural level, the renewal of thinking in accordance with modern requirements. It is impossible to imagine the effectiveness of the management of nature protection activities in society without understanding the ecological consequences of scientific and technological progress, the features of their globalization, the spiritual and moral essence.

From the first years of independence in Uzbekistan, serious attention was paid to the organization of environmental relations in accordance with the requirements and opportunities of the modern world. The legal framework, socio-economic, political, spiritual and educational conditions for the organization, management and control of work in this area on a democratic basis have been created. Because without it, it was impossible to stop the ecological crisis that occurred during the colonial period in the country, to normalize relations with the natural environment, to develop the ecological consciousness and culture of our people.

From this point of view, today the management activity of the state in the field of ecological relations is clearly reflected in its work in the field of legislation. At the same time, its legislative activity aimed at solving problems related to the environmental situation in society is of particular importance. At present, the Law "On Nature Protection", the Law "On Water and Water Use", the Law "On Groundwater", the Law "On Separate Landscaping"

The Law on Zones, the Law on the Protection and Use of Wildlife, the Law on State Sanitary Control and other laws are the legal basis of environmental ethics and culture in the state environmental policy.

The legislative activity of the state is a continuous process, which plays an important role in the implementation of all documents related to the protection of nature and the environment.

The existence and essence of these laws means that the legal management of all major activities related to nature is consistent with universal human principles. Accordingly, the essence, content and tasks that serve to strengthen the spiritual and moral foundations of social and ecological relations arising from the general content of the laws developed and implemented are: doirAs a rule, as noted in the scientific literature, “One of the important aspects of the radical reform of all aspects of life in modern Uzbekistan is a new approach to solving environmental problems. The position of the country's leadership in this regard is expressed in the theses of the National Action Plan on Environmental Protection, presented in a joint report of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the World Bank. The plan aims to improve environmental conditions, promote the efficient and sustainable use of natural resources, and protect the most sensitive and valuable resources of the ecosystem. In fact, it is an environmental rehabilitation program, which is almost the most important condition for the country's path to sustainable development. ” “The draft local budget expenditure plans and methodology focus on the practical solution of environmental problems and the best practices of environmental management. It brings together more than 20 environmental organizations, whose plans have been recognized as an effective model of governance. This international organization focuses on issues such as seeking local funding and attracting donor funds and foreign investors for the implementation of environmental and conservation projects in Central Asia. The goal of his program "Environmental Education and Enlightenment for Sustainable Development" is to address the universal problems of education and has played an important role in cultivating an ecological moral culture.

Separation of ecologically protected objects (enterprises, reserves). According to experts, 301 species of plants and 63 subspecies of vertebrates are on the verge of extinction in Uzbekistan¹. With the development of industrial and agricultural production, the number of plant and animal species continues to decline, as the area in which plants and animals can live in their natural conditions in the country is shrinking. Reserves under the Government of the Republic of Tajikistan to some

extent contribute to the expansion and enrichment of natural resources of flora and fauna of the republic. In addition, the forested areas of national parks protect water, performs a sanitary function in regulation. For example, mature spruce forests retain 4 to 27 percent of rainwater, while coconuts retain 10 to 21 percent, respectively. One hectare of protected forests is 24 thousand cubic meters. meters of irrigation water. In addition, juniper forest produces phytoncides (which kill plant-derived bacteria), which have antiseptic (wound disinfection) properties.

At the same time, it also acts as a filter. For example, it has been calculated that tukaizor retains up to 70% of airborne dust during growth. One hectare of turkey absorbs 8 kilograms of carbon dioxide in one hour. This is equal to the amount of carbon dioxide emitted when 200 people breathe. The national parks are a place of rest and maintain a healthy recreation environment. ” In this case, “the status of a nature reserve, national park or sanctuary for each individual area protected by nature is determined by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted on May 7, 1993 by the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This is the law appropriate reserves are a nature conservation research institution. ”. In this regard, this law has great practical and scientific significance. Sanctuaries are not only objects of nature conservation and protection, but also places of ecological morality and culture.

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